

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
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государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

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доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
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Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

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доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
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акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

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медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
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UDK 616.728.3-089

KHOLKHUJAYEV Farrukh Ikromovich
PhD
ONORBOYEV Dilmurod Abdusattorovich
Samarkand State Medical University

RESULTS OF PLASTY OF THE ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT USING THE HAMSTRING TENDONS.

For citation: Kholkhudjaye I. Farrukh, Onorboyev A. Dilmurod. Results of plasty of the anterior cruciate ligament using the hamstring tendons. // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 4, pp.368-373

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710302>

ABSTRACT

Stable, reliable minimally invasive surgical treatment for anterior cruciate ligament injury using tendons of thin and semi-tendon muscles using Ultrabutton Smith-Nephew.

The work is based on the experience of treating 110 patients with anterior cruciate ligament injuries in Samarkand branch of the republican scientific and practical medical center of traumatology and orthopedics, where the technique of plastic surgery using tendons of thin, semi-tendon muscles was used in the period from 2020 to 2022.

Excellent results - 42 (38.1%) - 85-90 points, good results - 64 (58,2%) – 65-85 points, satisfactory - 3 (2,8%) - up to 65 points, 1 (0,9%) patient retained slightly pronounced sensations of stiffness and discomfort in the joint until 1 year after surgery, which were stopped over time against the background of a rehabilitation program including physical therapy, physiotherapy, a course of chondroprotectors and intra-articular injections of synovial fluid protectors.

Autografts from the tendons of the popliteal hip flexors have been successfully used to restore the stability of knee joints with a damaged anterior ligament in both acute and chronic situations. This technique is a highly effective way to prevent the occurrence of complications, especially problems with stiffness and patellar pain.

Keywords: restoration of the ACL, Ultrabutton Smith-Nephew, instability of the knee joint.

ХОЛХУЖАЕВ Фарух Икромович
PhD

ОНОРБОЕВ Дилмурод Абдусатторович
Самаркандский Государственный медицинский университет

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ АРТРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ АУТОПЛАСТИКИ ПРИ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯХ ПЕРЕДНЕЙ КРЕСТООБРАЗНОЙ СВЯЗКИ КОЛЕННОГО СУСТАВА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Стабильное надежное малоинвазивное оперативное лечение при повреждении передней крестообразной связки с использованием сухожилий тонкой и полусухожильной мышц с использованием Ultrabutton Smith-Nephew .

Работа основана на опыте лечения 110 больных с повреждениями передней крестообразной связки в СФРНПМЦТиО, где была использована методика пластики с использованием сухожилий тонкой, полусухожильной мышц в период с 2020 по 2022 гг.

Отличные результаты – 42 (38,1%) - 85-90 балл, хорошие результаты - 64 (58,2%) – 65-85 балл, удовлетворительные – 3 (2,8%) – до 65 баллов, у 1 больного (0,9%) до 1 года после операции сохранялись незначительно выраженные ощущения скованности и дискомфорта в суставе, которые купировались с течением времени на фоне реабилитационной программы, включающей ЛФК, физиопроцедуры, курс хондропротекторов и внутрисуставные инъекции протекторов синовиальной жидкости.

Аутотрансплантаты из сухожилий подколенных сгибателей бедра успешно использованы для восстановления стабильности коленных суставов с поврежденной передней связкой как при острых, так и при хронических ситуациях. Данная методика является высокоэффективным способом профилактики возникновения осложнений, особенно проблем с туго подвижностью и надколенниковыми болями.

Ключевые слова: восстановление ПКС, Ultrabutton Smith-Nephew, нестабильность коленного сустава.

XOLXO‘JAEV Farrux Ikromovich

PhD

ONORBOEV Dilmurod Abduattorovich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

**TIZZA BO‘G‘IMI OLDINGI XOCHSIMON BOG‘LAMINING ESKI JAROHATLARIDA
ARTROSKOPIK USULDA AUTOPLASTIKA QILISH NATIJALARI**

ANNOTATSIYA

Tizza osti bukuvchi paylari, jumladan, ingichka va yarimpaysimion muskullar bilan Ultrabutton Smit-Nephew yordamida oldingi xochsimon bog‘lamalarining jarohatlarini plastika qilish - barqaror ishonchli kaminvaziv jarrohlik davolash imkonini beradi.

Ushbu tadqiqot RITOIATMSFda oldingi xochsimon bog‘lamaning (ACL) jarohati bo‘lgan 110 bemorlarni davolash tajribasiga asoslangan bo‘lib, unda 2020 va 2022 yillar oralig‘ida ingichka va yarimpaysimion muskullar bilan Ultrabutton Smit-Nephew yordamida plastika usuli qo‘llanilgan.

Zo‘r natijalar-42 (38,1%) – 85-90 ball; Yaxshi natijalar 64 (58,2%) – 65-85 ball; Qoniqarli natijalar-3 (2,8%) – 65 ballgacha. 1 ta (0,9%) bemorda operatsiyadan keyingi 1 yilgacha bo‘lgan davrda tizza bo‘g‘imida diskomfort va noqulaylik hissi kam darajada sezilishi saqlanib qolgan. Keyinchalik LFK, fizioterapiya muolajalari, xondroprotektorlar kursi va sinovial suyuqlik protektorlarining intraartikulyar inyeksiyasini o‘z ichiga olgan rehabilitatsiya dasturining fonida vaqt o‘tishi bilan yo‘qolgan.

Oldingi xochsimon bog‘lamalarining o‘tkir va surunkali jarohatlarida tizza bo‘g‘imining nostabilligini tiklash uchun tizza osti bukuvchi paylaridan olingan autotransplantanti muvaffaqiyatli ishlatilgan. Bu usul turli xildagi asoratlarni, ayniqsa, tizza bo‘g‘imidagi og‘riqlar va harakatni chegaralanishi kabi asoratlarni profilaktikasining yuqori samarali usuli hisoblanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ACL ni tiklash, Ultrabutton Smit-Nephew, tizza bo‘g‘imining nostabilligi.

Introduction. The restoration of the damaged ligaments of the knee joint is still a very serious task for traumatologists and orthopedists. Of particular importance is the arthroscopic restoration of the ligaments of the knee joint, namely the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL), which occupies the first place in terms of the frequency of injuries among all injuries of the ligaments of the knee joint [1,3,6].

Traumatologists and orthopedists often face this problem. Various implants and biodegrading screws are used in the restoration of the PCC [2,5]. But when using these implants and biodegrading screws, various variants of complications are also noted, such as a possible fracture of the lower edge of the created channel in the femur, migration of implants and screws into the joint cavity, difficulty in creating a channel at the anatomical place of attachment of the PCC [4,7,8]. We performed arthroscopic restoration of the PC in 110 patients using Ultrabutton Smith-Nephew, which is easy to do and the above complications are not observed.

Relevance. Knee joint ligament injuries occupy the first place in frequency and account for 50 to 75% of all knee joint injuries [4]. The main contingent of patients with anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries are young people of working age, leading a physically active lifestyle, engaged in sports [3]. Currently, the most optimal method of treating fresh and long-standing injuries of the ligamentous apparatus of the knee joint is operative [2].

The introduction of arthroscopic technologies and modern implants into a wide clinical practice currently allows us to offer the most effective methods of surgical treatment for knee joint instability, as well as to approach the treatment of such patients differentially, using different methods of surgical treatment depending on the requirements of patients for their future lifestyle. Despite the successes achieved in recent decades in knee reconstructive surgery, currently from 15% to 25% of patients suffer from instability and (or) pain after reconstructive plastic surgery of the anterior cruciate ligament [5,8]. Subsequently, this inevitably leads to the development of osteoarthritis of the knee joint.

The aim of the study. Stable reliable minimally invasive surgical treatment for damage to the anterior cruciate ligament using thin and semi-tendon muscles.

Materials and methods. The work is based on the experience of treating 110 patients with anterior cruciate ligament injuries in the Samarkand branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics, where the technique of plastic surgery using tendons of thin, semi-tendon muscles was used in the period from 2020 to 2022. The patients ranged in age from 18 to 42 years. There were 98 (89.4%) men and 12 (10.6%) women among the patients (diagram 1). All patients underwent plastic surgery of the anterior cruciate ligament of the tendons of the thin and semi-tendon muscles. The purpose of preoperative planning was to determine the degree of instability of the joint.

Diagram 1

In addition to the clinical examination, all patients underwent magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Concomitant meniscal and lateral ligament injuries were found in 99 patients. Isolated rupture of the PCC was diagnosed in 11 patients (Table 1).

Table 1

Total number of patients	110	100 %
Isolated anterior cruciate ligament injury (ACL)	11	9.9%
Rupture of the PCC in combination with damage to the menisci and lateral ligaments	99	90.1 %

All patients underwent autotendoplasty using tendons of thin and semi-tendon muscles. The graft was fixed on the femoral canal using an Ultra button Smith-Nephew on the tibial canal with biodegradable Smith-Nephew and (or) Conmed implants (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The advantages of this fixation technique are as follows:

1. When fixing the Ultra button, the femoral canal is created at the site of anatomical attachment of the anterior cruciate ligament.
2. A possible fracture of the lower wall of the canal in the femur is excluded, which sometimes occurs when fixing with interference screws.
3. The migration of the implant and getting into the joint cavities is excluded.
4. It is easy to perform, and also the fixation will be reliable.

The average length of the femoral canal during its formation from the medial port was 20 (+5) mm, the average length of the tibial canal was 50 ± 5 mm. The diameter of the femoral and tibial canals was 8.5 ± 1.0 mm. The average length of the graft from the tendons of the thin and semi-tendon muscles and (or) the tendon of the long fibular muscle was 105 ± 15 mm.

Research results:

Studied in 110 patients on the Lysholm scale. The Lysholm scale is based on an assessment of 8 parameters, up to 100 points: pain - no – 25 points, is - 0; joint instability – no – 25 points, is – 0 points; joint blockage – no – 15 points, is - 0 points; joint edema – no – 25 points, is – 0 points; chromata – no – 5 points, there are - 0 points; climbing stairs – there are – 10 points, no – 0 points; squats – free – 5 points, limited – 0 points; needs help – no – 5 points, there are - 0 points.

Excellent results – 42 (38.1%) – 85-90 points;

Good results - 64 (58.2%) – 65-85 points;

Satisfactory – 3 (2.8%) – up to 65 points (Diagram 2).

In 1 (0.9%) patients, up to 1 year after surgery, slightly pronounced sensations of stiffness and discomfort in the joint remained, which were stopped over time against the background of a rehabilitation program including physical therapy, physiotherapy, a course of chondroprotectors and intra-articular injections of synovial protectors liquids.

Diagram 2

Conclusion.

Autografts from the tendons of the popliteal hip flexors have been successfully used to restore the stability of knee joints with a damaged anterior ligament in both acute and chronic situations. This technique is a highly effective way to prevent the occurrence of complications, especially problems with stiffness and patellar pain.

The presented experience of using surgical methods of treatment for various forms of instability of the knee joint indicates the need for a differentiated approach to the choice of operational tactics. The proposed tactics of surgical treatment for anterior instability of the knee joint provides:

- firstly, the relative simplicity and reproducibility of surgical techniques with minimal risk of intraoperative complications;
- secondly, the maximum possible restoration of the anatomy and function of the knee joint;
- thirdly, the reliability and strength of fixation, which will allow patients to return to their previous level of physical activity in the shortest possible time.

The proposed method is very relevant in modern conditions and should be used in athletes and people leading an active lifestyle.

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Статья поступила в редакцию 11.07.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 21.08.2024; принята к публикации 24.08.2024.

The article was submitted 11.07.2024; approved after reviewing 21.08.2024; accepted for publication 24.08.2024.

Информация об авторах:

Холхужаев Фаррух Икромович- PhD, ассистент, кафедры травматологии и ортопедии. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: farrux.xolxujayev@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0823-5124>.

Оноройев Дилмурод Абдусатторович- клиник ординатор кафедры травматологии и ортопедии. Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, Самарканд, Узбекистан. E-mail: farrux.xolxujayev@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0823-5110>.

Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Холхужаев Ф.И. — идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи;

Оноройев Д.А. — сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Kholkhuzhaev Farrukh Ikromovich - PhD, Assistant, Department of Traumatology and Orthopedics. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. E-mail: farrux.xolxujayev@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0823-5124>.

Onorboev Dilmurod Abdusattorovich is a clinical resident of the Department of Traumatology and Orthopedics. Samarkand State Medical University, Samarkand, Uzbekistan. E-mail: farrux.xolxujayev@mail.ru , <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0823-5110>.

Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Kholkhuzhaev F.I.— ideological concept of the work, writing the text; editing the article;

Onorboev D.A.— collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 4

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